

Theory Of Everything And The Possibility Of Ancient Aliens

By

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Important To Point Out

You can speak of the structure of the solar system even though it changes with time. This is important to understand when I refer to sizes of the Moon and the planets, and their orbital distances.

The whole object of developing a theory for the way planetary systems form is that they meet the following criterion: They predict the Titius-Bode rule for the distribution of the planets; the distribution gives the planetary orbital periods from Newton's Universal Law of Gravitation. The distribution of the planets is chiefly predicted by three factors: The inward forces of gravity from the parent star, the outward pressure gradient from the stellar production of radiation, and the outward inertial forces as a cloud collapses into a flat disc around the central star. These forces separate the flat disc into rings, agglomerations of material, each ring from which a different planet forms at its central distance from the star (it has a thickness). In a theory of planetary formation from a primordial disc, it should predict the Titius-Bode rule for the distribution of planets today, which was the distribution of the rings from which the planets formed.

Abstract

This paper describes planetary systems, atomic systems, and biological systems under one idea, as such it is kind of a theory of everything.

In Part 1 of this paper I show that the system of measuring time we have today, that divides the day into 24 hours and the hours into 60 minutes, and the minutes into 60 seconds, that came to us from the ancient Sumerians, who divided the day into 24 hours, and who gave us the base 60 counting that resulted in our base unit of time, the second, to have the duration it has today, was a choice that happens to coincide with my theory that shows that our Earth/Moon/Sun system and atomic systems have a solution in common of the Schrödinger wave equation with the same base unit of time of 1 second.

The ancient Sumerians were the first to settle down from wandering, following the herds and hunting them with stone spearpoint to invent agriculture, architecture, mathematics, astronomy, and writing. They gave us civilization as we know it today. Since their second came to us from their system of counting and I have found the second to be a base unit and natural constant for our planetary system and atomic systems in common, I think it is reasonable to suggest that perhaps they were given their system of mathematics by ancient Aliens. This is easy to suggest because their writings say they were given their knowledge by "Those who came from above."

In Part 2 of this paper I show evidence in support of this ancient alien hypothesis, that they may have left a trace in their time measurements in UFO activity in Manitoba Canada that connects with an ancient number the Sumerians wrote down on clay tablets thousands of years ago.

Part 3 I have a theory for the star systems, the planets and their suns, wherein such systems are solved with the Schrödinger wave equation that is used to solve atomic systems. The result is that star systems and atomic systems, systems on the macro scales and micro scales, are governed by the same underlying principles. It came to pass that this theory indicated an overlap with biological systems indicating that biological life could be part of the same idea. Here I develop that.

Part 4 Our solution of the wave equation for the planets gives the kinetic energy of the Earth from the mass of the Moon orbiting the Earth, but you could formulate based on the Earth orbiting the Sun.

Part 5 We want to find what the wave equation solutions are for Jupiter and Saturn because they significantly carry the majority of the mass of the solar system and thus should embody most clearly the dynamics of the wave solution to the Solar System.

Part 6 We want to solve a habitable planetary system in general and apply it to another star system. We must include the solution of its moon as well, because the Moon of the Earth makes life optimally possible.

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Part 1: The Sumerians Give Us The Unit of a Second Which Turns Out To Be A Natural Constant

While we can measure time by the completion of the Earth in its orbit around the Sun, 365.25 days, or by the rotation of the Earth once in 24 hours giving us the 24 hour day, we measure the day by a division of it into 24 equal units we call the hour because the ancient Sumerians divided the day from sunrise to sunset into 12 hours because they could measure time in the day by the Sun's position in the sky as determined by a shadow cast by it on the ground that moves through 12 divisions in a day, each division called an hour. 12 hours are then added on for the night from sunset to sunrise, so we have the 24 hour day from sunrise to sunrise, or sunset to sunset. But why choose 12 divisions which gives us the duration of the hour? I believe the reason is because 12 is the first abundant number. An abundant number means it is divisible evenly by so many integers preceding it, that their sum is greater than the number itself. That is, 12 is evenly divisible by 1,2,3,4,6 which is greater than 12:

$$1+2+3+4+6=16>12$$

There is more reason to choose 12 and that is what it is divisible by. Firstly it is divisible by the two smallest primes 2 and 3, the factors by which no integer can be reduced to further. 2 times 3 is 6 and 12 is evenly divisible by 6 and 6 is of primary importance in mathematics in that the six-sided regular polygon, the regular hexagon, has its radii equal in lengths to its sides, something, for one thing, that makes it easy as a tool for computing pi (π) the ratio of the circumference of a circle to its diameter. This because inscribed in a circle it approximates the circle, meaning its perimeter of six, if each side is taken as one, gives its diameter is two, meaning π is close to six divided by two is three. Further twelve is evenly divisible by 4, and the four-sided square is one of the regular polygons that tessellate meaning the square can tile a surface without leaving gaps. This makes it suitable for a coordinate system to specify a point in the plane or space. Such a coordinate system is the first we learn of in school, and is the most used, in fact other coordinate systems are defined in terms of it like spherical systems where the angle is measured from a set of rectangular axes.

The other two regular polygons that tessellate are the equilateral triangle and our regular hexagon.

The Sumerians use a base 60 (sexagesimal) counting system because 60 is evenly divisible by so much as well:

1,2,3,4,5,6,10, 12, 15, 20, 30

Making it an abundant number as well, it adds up to 108, which is much greater than 60. It is important to have 5 because in the regular pentagon it determines the golden ratio, phi (ϕ), which is recurrent throughout Nature. Life more often meets up with 5-fold symmetry, like a starfish with five arms, a human with two legs, two arms, and a head, or five fingers on each hand. The physical more often meets up with six-fold symmetry, like in the points on a snowflake. We then have our base unit of one second comes from dividing our day into 24 hours and each of those hours into 60 minutes, and each of those minutes into 60 seconds. Thus the unit of a second comes to us from the ancient Sumerians, but I find the unit of a second is a natural constant for the the atom and the solar system.

So we have to ask did ancient aliens give the Sumerians their method of measuring time with the 24 hour day, and base 60 sexagesimal counting. Indeed, they were the first to settle down from hunting with stone spearpoint and following the herds to invent agriculture, architecture, mathematics, and writing and their myths say they were given this knowledge from "Those who came from the above".

This second I found is the base unit of the orbital dynamics of the solar system. I found I could create three operators, one that acts on the radius of the proton to its mass, and the other that acts on the radius of the Sun to its mass, and one that acts on angular momentum to speed. h is Planck's constant, G is the universal constant of gravitation, c is the speed of light, α is the fine structure constant, r_p is the radius of a proton, m_p is the mass of a proton, M_m is the mass of the Moon, R_m is its radius, and the EarthDay is the rotation period of the Earth:

$$1) \quad \left(\frac{1}{6\alpha^2} \sqrt{\frac{4\pi h}{Gc}} \right) \cdot \frac{r_p}{m_p} = 1second$$

$$2) \quad \left(\frac{M_m(EarthDay)}{R_m} \right) \cdot \frac{R_\odot}{M_\odot} = 1second$$

$$3) \quad \left(\sqrt{\frac{2}{3} \cdot \frac{\pi r_p}{\alpha^4 G m_p^3}} \right) \frac{1}{3} \cdot \frac{h_p}{c} = 1second$$

They seem to suggest that the Earth orbit might be quantized in terms of the Moon and a base unit of one second.

We say there is a Planck constant for the solar system. We do it with a base unit of one second because equations 1 and 2 suggest we should. We suggest it is such that it is given by the standard Planck constant for the atom, h , times some constant, C , and the Kinetic energy of the Earth.

$$4) \quad \hbar_\odot = (hC)KE_e$$

$$5) \quad hC = 1second$$

Where

$$6). \quad C = \frac{1}{3} \cdot \frac{1}{\alpha^2 c} \sqrt{\frac{2}{3} \cdot \frac{\pi r_p}{G m_p^3}}$$

Where equation 6 comes from equation 3.

We derive the value of our solar Planck constant

$$C = \frac{1}{3} \cdot \frac{1}{\alpha^2 c} \sqrt{\frac{1}{3} \cdot \frac{2\pi r_p}{G m_p^3}} =$$

$$\frac{1}{3} \cdot \frac{18769}{299792458} \sqrt{\frac{1}{3} \cdot \frac{2\pi(0.833E - 15)}{(6.67408E - 11)(1.67262E - 27)^3}}$$

$$=1.55976565E33$$

$$= \frac{s}{m} \sqrt{\frac{m}{kg^3} \cdot \frac{s^2 kg}{m^3}} = \frac{s}{m} \sqrt{\frac{s^2}{kg^2 m^2}} = \frac{s}{m} \cdot \frac{s}{kg \cdot m} = \frac{1}{kg} \cdot \frac{s^2}{m^2}$$

$$\frac{1}{C} = kg \frac{m^2}{s^2} = \frac{1}{2} m v^2 = \text{energy}$$

$$hC = (6.62607E - 34)(1.55976565E33) = 1.03351 \text{seconds} \approx 1.0 \text{seconds}$$

$$hC = \left(kg \frac{m}{s^2} \cdot m \cdot s \right) \left(\frac{1}{kg} \cdot \frac{s^2}{m^2} \right)$$

$$= \left(kg \frac{m^2}{s} \right) \left(\frac{1}{kg} \cdot \frac{s^2}{m^2} \right) = \text{seconds}$$

$$KE_{\text{earth}} = \frac{1}{2} (5.972E24 kg) (30,290 m/s)^2 = 2.7396E33 J$$

$$\hbar_{\odot} = (hC) KE_{\text{earth}} = (1.03351 s) (2.7396E33 J) = 2.8314E33 J \cdot s$$

Now we show that our Planck constant for the solar system gives the base unit of one second for the quantization. We call our solar Planck constant \hbar_{\odot} and find the wavelength for the Moon which is the ground state for the solar system:

$$7) \quad \lambda_{\text{moon}} = \frac{\hbar_{\odot}^2}{GM_m^3} = \frac{(2.8314E33)^2}{(6.67408E - 11)(7.34763E22 kg)^3} = 3.0281E8 m$$

Then wavelength associated with the Moon divided by the speed of light should be 1 second if our planetary system is quantized in terms of the Moon and a base unit of one second. We have

$$8) \quad \frac{\lambda_{\text{moon}}}{c} = \frac{3.0281E8 m}{299,792,458 m/s} = 1.010 \text{seconds}$$

And we see it is, so we have

$$9) \quad \frac{\lambda_{\text{moon}}}{c} = 1 \text{second}$$

The solution for the orbit of the Earth around Sun with the Schrödinger wave equation can be inferred from the solution for an electron around a proton in the a hydrogen atom with the Schrödinger wave equation. The Schrödinger wave equation is, in spherical coordinates

10)

$$-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \left[\frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r^2 \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \right) + \frac{1}{r^2 \sin \theta} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \left(\sin \theta \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \right) + \frac{1}{r^2 \sin^2 \theta} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \phi^2} \right] \psi + V(r)\psi = E\psi$$

Its solution for the atom is

$$11) \quad E = -\frac{Z^2(k_e e^2)^2 m_e}{2\hbar^2 n^2}$$

$$12) \quad r_n = \frac{n^2 \hbar^2}{Z k_e e^2 m_e}$$

E is the energy for an electron orbiting Z protons and r_n , is the orbital shell for an electron with Z protons, n the orbital number. I find the solution for the Earth around the Sun utilizes the Moon around the Earth. This is different than with the atom because planets and moons are not all the same size and mass like electrons and protons are, and they don't jump from orbit to orbit like electrons do. I find that for the Earth around the Sun

$$13) \quad KE_e = \sqrt{n} \frac{R_\odot}{R_m} \cdot \frac{G^2 M_e^2 M_m^3}{2\hbar_\odot^2}$$

$$14) \quad r_n = \frac{2\hbar_\odot^2}{GM_m^3} \cdot \frac{R_\odot}{R_m} \cdot \frac{1}{\sqrt{n}}$$

KE_e is the kinetic energy of the Earth, and r_n is the planet's orbit. R_\odot is the radius of the Sun, r_m is the radius of the Moon's orbit, M_e is the mass of the Earth, M_m is the mass of the Moon, n is the orbit number of the Earth which is 3 and \hbar_\odot is the Planck constant for the solar system. Instead of having Z protons, we have R_\odot/R_m the radius of the Sun normalized by the radius of the Moon. It is has always been an amazing fact the the sizes of the Moon and the Sun are such that given their orbital distances, the Moon as seen from the Earth perfectly eclipses the Sun. This becomes part of the theory and we suggest it is a condition for sophisticated planets that harbor life by writing it:

$$15) \quad \frac{r_{planet}}{r_{moon}} \approx \frac{R_{star}}{R_{moon}}$$

That is the orbital radius of the planet (Earth) to the orbital radius of its moon (The Moon) is about equal to the the radius of the star (The Sun) to the radius of its moon (The Moon). We say the system is quantized by the Moon and the base unit of one second. It is a fact that the Moon orbiting the Earth optimizes the conditions for life on Earth because it holds the Earth at its inclination to its orbit around the Sun allowing for the seasons, preventing extreme hot and extreme cold. Let us now see if our solar Planck constant works...

$$16) \quad \frac{R_\odot}{R_m} = \frac{6.96E8m}{1737400m} = 400.5986$$

$$KE_e = (1.732)(400.5986) \frac{(6.67408E-11)^2 (5.972E24kg)^2 (7.347673E22kg)^3}{2(2.8314E33)^2} =$$

$$= 2.727E36J$$

The kinetic energy of the Earth is

$$KE_e = \frac{1}{2} (5.972E24kg) (30,290m/s)^2 = 2.7396E33J$$

The accuracy of our equation is:

$$\frac{2.727E36J}{2.7396E33J} 100 = 99.5 \%$$

Which is very good. Thus we have solved the Earth/Moon/Sun System with our spacetime operators by using them to find a Planck constant for the solar system.

We want to suggest that the base 60 dynamic applied to the rotational velocity of the Earth to measure time has a natural property associated with the atom and the Earth/Moon/Sun orbital system as a solution to the atom's wave equation. The Earth day is given by, in seconds

$$\left(\frac{1day}{24hrs} \right) \left(\frac{1hr}{60min} \right) \left(\frac{1min}{60sec} \right) = \frac{1}{186400} \frac{day}{sec}$$

This gives since $2 \cdot 3 \cdot 4 = 24$

$$2 \cdot 3 \cdot 4 \cdot 60 \cdot 60 = 86400seconds/day$$

Thus we have as factors for the seconds per day the smallest primes 2 and 3, and the 4 of rectangular coordinate systems, and the versatile, abundant, 60. We then suggest the second is dynamic in terms of what the ancients gave us because 86400 seconds comes from $2 \cdot 3 \cdot 4 \cdot 60 \cdot 60$ and this I suggest is connected to Nature because the Earth rotates at a speed that gives from these ancient factors the duration of a second that I found is the base unit of the atomic systems and our planetary system, in particular of our Earth/Moon/Sun system as a solution of the Schrödinger wave equation that solves the same atomic system, which I will go into right now.

We see the spacetime operators solve the atom by giving us the radius of a proton. We set equation 3 equal to equation 1

$$3) \quad \left(\sqrt{\frac{2}{3} \cdot \frac{\pi r_p}{\alpha^4 G m_p^3}} \right) \frac{1}{3} \cdot \frac{h}{c} = 1second$$

$$1). \quad \left(\frac{1}{6\alpha^2} \sqrt{\frac{4\pi h}{Gc}} \right) \cdot \frac{r_p}{m_p} = 1second$$

These two yield

$$17). \quad r_p = \frac{2}{3} \cdot \frac{h}{cm_p}$$

I find this is close to the experimental value of the radius of a proton. I find I can arrive at this radius of a proton another way, energy is given by Planck's constant and frequency

$$E = hf$$

We have

$$f = 1/s, h = J \cdot s, hf = (J \cdot s)(1/s) = J$$

$$E = J = \text{Joules} = \text{energy}$$

We take the rest energy of the mass of a proton m_p :

$$E = m_p c^2$$

The frequency of a proton is

$$f_p = \frac{m_p c^2}{h}$$

Since our theory gave us the factor of $2/3$ for the radius of a proton we have:

$$\frac{m_p c^2}{h} \cdot \frac{r_p}{c} = \frac{2}{3} \approx \phi = \frac{m_p c}{h} r_p$$

$$m_p r_p = \frac{2}{3} \cdot \frac{h}{c}$$

The radius of a proton is then

$$r_p = \frac{2}{3} \cdot \frac{h}{cm_p}$$

This is close to the CODATA value for the proton radius around 2018 ($0.842E-15m$). The result is

$$r_p = \frac{2}{3} \cdot \frac{6.62607E-34}{(299,792,458)(1.67262E-27)} = 0.88094E-15m$$

We find it may be that the radius of a proton is actually

$$18) \quad r_p = \phi \cdot \frac{h}{cm_p} = 0.816632E-15m$$

Where ϕ is the golden ratio constant (0.618...). This is more along the lines of more recent measurements. Both equations 17 and 18 for the radius of the proton can be right depending on the dynamics of what is going on; the radius of a proton is not precisely defined, it is more of a fuzzy cloud of subatomic particles. Thus we have solved the atom with our spacetime operators by producing the radius of a proton.

Indeed if the dynamics of the factors the ancients gave us to create the duration of a second are connected to the dynamics of stars systems then then the second should define the rotational angular momentum of the Earth since we divide the rotation period of the Earth into these factors to get the unit of second, and should be connected to our Planck constant for the solar system which is in units of angular momentum as well, as is Planck's constant for the atom.

The angular momentum of the Earth with respect to the Sun is $2.66E40$ kg m²/s. The rotational angular momentum is $7.05E33$ kg m²/s. In orbit angular momentum is given by

$$L = 2\pi Mfr^2$$

For a uniform rotational sphere it is given by

$$L = \frac{4}{5}\pi Mfr^2$$

We found our solar system Planck constant was

$$\hbar_{\odot} = 2.8314E33J \cdot s$$

This gives

$$19) \quad \frac{L_{earth}}{\hbar_{\odot}} = \frac{7.05E33}{2.8314E33} = 2.4899 \approx 2.5 = 2\frac{1}{2}$$

We are now equipped to show that the ancient Sumerians were right in dividing the rotation period of the Earth (the day) into 24 units (the hour) because

$$2.5(24) = 60$$

That is

$$20). \quad \frac{L_{earth}}{\hbar_{\odot}} 24 = 60$$

Which is to say the angular momentum of the Earth to its Planck constant gives the base 60 counting in terms of the 24 hour day, the 60 of 60 minutes in an hour, and 60 seconds in a minute, that determine our base unit of duration we call a second that happens to be, as I have shown, the base unit of the wave solution to the atom and the Earth/Moon/Sun system.

Our equation in this paper for the Earth energy as a solution of the wave equation (eq. 13)

$$13). \quad KE_e = \sqrt{n} \frac{R_{\odot}}{R_m} \cdot \frac{G^2 M_e^2 M_m^3}{2\hbar_{\odot}^2}$$

does not depend on the Moon's distance from the Earth, only its mass. The Moon slows the Earth rotation and this in turn expands the Moon's orbit, so it is getting larger, the Earth loses energy to the Moon. The Earth day gets longer by 0.0067 hours per million years, and the Moon's orbit gets 3.78 cm larger per year. Equation 20

$$20) \frac{L_{earth}}{\hbar_{\odot}} 24 = 60$$

only specifies divide the day into 24 units, and hours into 60 minutes and minutes into 60 seconds, regardless of what the Earth rotational velocity is. But it was more or less the same as it is now when the Sumerians started civilization. But it may be that it holds for when the Earth day is such that when the Moon perfectly eclipses the Sun, which we said might be a condition for the optimization of life preventing extreme hot and cold. That is when 15 holds

$$15) \frac{r_{planet}}{r_{moon}} \approx \frac{R_{star}}{R_{moon}}$$

Which holds for today and held for the ancient Sumerians and holds for when the Earth rotation gives the duration of a second we have today.

We want the basis set of equations for the solar system. We have

$$\lambda_{moon} = \frac{\hbar_{\odot}^2}{GM_m^3} = 3.0281E8m$$

We have from equation

$$\frac{\lambda_{moon}}{c} = \frac{\hbar_{\odot}^2}{GM_m^3} \cdot \frac{1}{c} = 1.0seconds$$

We have equations

$$\hbar_{\odot} = (hC)KE_e$$

$$hC = 1second$$

We have equations

$$\left(\sqrt{\frac{2}{3} \cdot \frac{\pi r_p}{\alpha^4 G m_p^3}} \right) \frac{1}{3} \cdot \frac{h}{c} = 1second$$

$$\left(\frac{1}{6\alpha^2} \sqrt{\frac{4\pi h}{Gc}} \right) \cdot \frac{r_p}{m_p} = 1second$$

$$1second = \frac{KE_m}{KE_e}(EarthDay)$$

From these it becomes clear that

$$21) \quad \hbar_{\odot} = \frac{GM_m^3 c}{KE_e}$$

$$22) \quad KE_e = \frac{GM_m^3 c}{\hbar_{\odot}}$$

$$23) \quad \hbar_{\odot} = \left(\frac{1}{6\alpha^2} \cdot \frac{r_p}{m_p} \sqrt{\frac{4\pi\hbar}{Gc}} \right) KE_e$$

Thus combining equation 20 with the following...

$$\frac{\lambda_{moon}}{c} = 1second$$

$$hC = 1second$$

$$\hbar_{\odot} = (hC)KE_e$$

$$21). \quad KE_e = \frac{GM_m^3 c}{\hbar_{\odot}}$$

$$20). \quad \frac{L_{earth}}{\hbar_{\odot}} 24 = 60$$

gives

$$1second = \left(\frac{24}{60} \right)^2 \frac{L_{earth}^2}{GM_m^3 c}$$

Which gives

$$\begin{aligned} 24) \quad 1second &= \left(\frac{24}{60} \right)^2 \frac{L_{earth}^2}{GM_m^3 c} \\ &= \left(\frac{24}{60} \right)^2 \frac{(7.05E33)^2}{(6.67408E-11)((7.347673E22kg)^3(299792458m/s)} = \\ &\left(\frac{24}{60} \right)^2 6.262sec = 1.002seconds = 1.00seconds \end{aligned}$$

This is very accurate to give us a second. But notice 6.262 is approximately 2π . We see that

$$25) \quad 1 = \left(\frac{24}{60}\right)^2 2\pi$$

2π is the circumference of a unit circle, it could be that the circumference of the Earth orbit, can be taken as 1 (unity) and essentially we have the mystery of base 60 and the 24 hour day of the ancient Sumerians is solved, it connects unit circle to 1 (unity).

$$26). \quad \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2} = \frac{24}{60}\sqrt{\pi}$$

$$27) \quad \cos(45^\circ) = \cos(\pi/4) = \frac{24}{60}\sqrt{\pi}$$

Part 2: Ancient Sumerians, Ancient Aliens, And UFO's Today

Abstract

After developing a a single theory for atomic systems and planetary systems, I have found that the unit of a second for measuring time, which ultimately came to us from the Ancient Sumerians, who first settled down from following the herds and hunting with stone spearpoint to invent writing, mathematics, agriculture and metallurgy along the Tigris and Euphrates rivers of Mesopotamia, is a Natural constant.

There has been some suggestion by many scholars that, since this invention of civilization by the Sumerians happened mysteriously almost overnight on an archaeological time scale, that they were given knowledge by Ancient Aliens.

I am able to suggest that traces of such Aliens may exist in ancient records and contemporary UFO sightings, and that the two are connected. I show this connection may be rooted in the idea of the unit of a second for measuring time as a Natural constant, that it is a basis unit for describing atomic systems, planetary systems, and biological systems in common.

Introduction

I developed a theory that solves both the atom and the solar system in terms of a base unit of 1 second and quantization of the system with the Earth's moon. When working out the theory the base unit of time came out to be 1 second, and I thought that was rather incredible because the second came to us ultimately from the Ancient Sumerians who mysteriously settled down from hunting with stone spearpoint and inventing agriculture, mathematics, and astronomy, but we would hazard to guess they didn't know about a wave equation solution for the solar system or the radius and mass of the atom's proton, let alone of the proton itself, that all came much later with modern science.

What was even more compelling was that this unit of a second occurred in many forms in terms of many different things in the theory. I found:

$$1second = \frac{KE_m}{KE_e}(EarthDay)$$

$$\left(\frac{1}{6\alpha^2} \sqrt{\frac{4\pi h}{Gc}} \right) \cdot \frac{r_p}{m_p} = 1second$$

$$\left(\sqrt{\frac{2}{3} \cdot \frac{\pi r_p}{\alpha^4 G m_p^3}} \right) \frac{1}{3} \cdot \frac{h}{c} = 1second$$

$$\frac{\lambda_{moon}}{c} = 1second$$

$$1second = d_e \frac{v_m}{v_e^2} \sqrt{\frac{M_m^3 \sqrt{3}}{M_e^2 M_\odot}}$$

Where KE_m is the kinetic energy of the Moon, KE_e is the kinetic energy of the Earth, α is the fine structure constant is 1/137, *EarthDay* is the rotation period of the Earth 24 hours, h is Planck's constant, G is the universal constant of gravitation, c is the speed of light, r_p is the radius of the proton, m_p is the mass of a proton, λ_{moon} is a wavelength associated with the Moon in the theory, M_m is the mass of the Moon, M_e is the mass of the Earth, M_\odot is the mass of the Sun, d_e is the diameter of the Earth's orbit, v_m is the orbital velocity of the Moon, and v_e is the orbital velocity of the Earth, 3 is the Earth orbital number.

In part 1 we already went into how I arrived at all that. I would like to go into the theory that we may have ultimately got our unit of a second for measuring time from ancient aliens who may have given it to the Ancient Sumerians who started civilization, the Ancient Sumerians from whom we got writing, mathematics, and agriculture.

We have the unit of a second today because the Ancient Sumerians had a base 60 system of counting (sexagesimal it is called). The Sumerians divided the day into 12 hours, evenly divisible into 60, and so from sunrise to sunrise was 24 hours, and from sunset to sunset was 24 hours. They multiplied 60 by 6, to get 360 degrees in a circle. Since the Earth does one orbit around the Sun in 365 days, which is a year, the Earth goes through about 1 degree a day. The Babylonians got that from them, and further divided the hour into 60 minutes, and the minute into 60 seconds, though hours were in their sun dials, they only used minutes and seconds for astronomy. The West, the Europeans, got their sun dials from the Babylonians but did not incorporate minutes and seconds into their mechanical clocks until the 17th century, but it all came from the Sumerians, who settled down from hunting with stone spearpoint and started agriculture, writing, mathematics, and civilization in general. Sun dials were used in Egypt as well and had 12 divisions throughout the day as well for hours. A sun dial simply tells time by the angle of a shadow cast by the Sun as the sun rises and sets, its position measuring time.

The interesting thing is that we have the duration of a second is what it is not because we were attempting to find some base unit of time for Nature, but rather we have the duration of a second from ancient times that came to us over many years of dividing the rotation of the Earth into hours, minutes, and seconds in such a way that we ended up with it. However we may have had some sort of a thought going into it that was six-fold in Nature that lead it to being natural if we consider:

$$1second = \frac{1}{365.25} \cdot \frac{1}{24} \cdot \frac{1}{60} \cdot \frac{1}{60} = 0.0000000316881year$$

And that thought may be was in a six-fold pattern that the motions of the Earth/Moon/Sun system had in it approximately which we inadvertently characterized in the calendar:

$$\left(\frac{360days}{year}\right) \left(\frac{24hours}{day}\right) \left(\frac{60min}{hour}\right) \left(\frac{60sec}{min}\right) = 31104000seconds/year$$

Which can be written

$$12^2 \left(\frac{60days}{year}\right) \left(\frac{1hour}{day}\right) \left(\frac{60min}{hour}\right) \left(\frac{60sec}{min}\right)$$

Where there are 360 degrees in a circle and as such the Earth approximately moves through one degree per day around the Sun. We achieved this because the ancients of Sumeria and Babylonia from which the ancient Greeks received their counting system used base 60, sexagesimal because 60 is evenly divisible by so much, that is by

1,2,3,4,5,6, 10, 12, 15, 20, 30,...

My Guess That Panned Out

I thought we might want to look for clues in present times for the possibility of aliens who may still be coming here, in the reports of UFO's.

I have undertaken this, and thought what a better way than to look at how we measure the ancient second with modern clocks. The ancients did it with the position of the Sun in the sky which comes from the rotation of the Earth, that turns once in 24 hours giving us the length of the day, but that is not a very precise way to do it because the rotation of the Earth can waver in

its period due to gravitational influences from other bodies in the solar system, like the Moon, the Sun, and the planets.

We started with sun dials in ancient times, moved to gear ratios for clocks in medieval and renaissance Europe, but in contemporary times we moved to oscillators, like the quartz crystal oscillators in digital wrist watches, which is much more accurate. After that we got more accurate with atomic clocks that make use of cesium. Quartz crystals and Cesium both occur in Nature, and we mine them for making clocks.

In the 1980s the advent of solid-state digital electronics allowed for quartz timekeepers and these are the mostly widely used today in most clocks and watches. If a quartz crystal is appropriately shaped it will oscillate at a frequency of 32768 Hz, that is, $32768=2^{15}$ oscillations per second. Thus we began to define the second as that many oscillations of a quartz crystal.

Of course, over a year, a watch made from quartz crystals might lose a second or two over a year, and more accurate is an atomic clock using cesium 133, the only stable isotope of cesium. The second is now defined by 9,192,631,770 cycles of oscillations of the cesium atom.

Thus the first place I looked in hopes of finding clues to the existence of extraterrestrials, extraterrestrials who may have given us the second in ancient times, was where cesium is found and mined. It turns out it is a rare element and its most abundant deposits are in the province of Manitoba in Canada, a place called Bernic Lake, in its South East corner. I then looked for UFO sightings in Manitoba, and to my surprise found the most well documented UFO sighting in Canada was there at Falcon Lake near the capitol Winnipeg which is right near Bernic Lake where Cesium for clocks to define the second is primarily mined.

Interestingly, the Falcon Lake UFO sighting was in 1967 (May 20), the year we defined the second with the cesium atomic clock, and was right near Bernic Lake where the cesium is primarily mined. It involved a ship landing and a geologist that saw it, and approached it, Stefan Michalak, who was hiking there looking for quartz deposits of all things, to stake a mining claim. I thought perhaps the extraterrestrials were in the area looking for cesium, or quartz (which occurs there as well) for their ship clocks.

To see the proximity of Falcon Lake of the UFO sighting, and Bernic Lake where Cesium is primarily mined, to one another, and with the capitol of the province of Manitoba, go to the maps on the next page...

1 hr 38 min (143.9 km) via Trans-Canada Hwy/MB-1 W

[Directions](#)

1 hr 57 min (164.7 km) via PR 317/MB-317 W/Provincial Rd 317 and Provincial Trunk Hwy 59 S

[Directions](#)

The Falcon Lake UFO Incident

Just how did the Falcon Lake UFO incident unfold? Steve Michalak was out inspecting a quartz vein when he he saw two objects hovering 45 meters (150 ft) away from him glowing red. One of the objects landed nearby and took on a disk shape. The other craft flew off. Before approaching the craft Steve sat and drew it for half an hour. He noticed the craft lacked any seams and had no insignias, and looked like smooth metal. It was 10.5 meters (34 ft) in diameter, and 4.5 meters in height (15 ft).

He noticed a door was open with light coming out, and heard voices of people talking. He attempted to communicate with them in English to offer mechanical support, but they did not respond and he tried in Polish, Russian, and German to no avail. He touched the craft and the fingertips of his gloves melted, it was so hot.

The craft then rotated revealing a grid of holes that emitted a blast of heated gas that hit him in the chest, setting his clothes a fire, which he took off and the craft flew away. After returning home he sought medical attention at Misericordia Health Center for his injuries and nausea where he was admitted to the emergency room. His injuries were confirmed by the doctors, with gridline burns on his chest and stomach. It was confirmed he had radiation poisoning. He was never convinced he saw a UFO that was alien but rather an experimental aircraft. The incident was investigated by the Royal Canadian Mounted Police, the Royal Canadian Air Force, The Department of Health, Department of National Defense, and American authorities the Aerial Phenomena Research Organization and the United States Air Force as a part of the Condon Committee. That is just a brief synopsis so I will leave the detailed story to books on the subject.

Cesium Clocks And the Ancient Constant of Nineveh

All that remains to be done now is to connect the Ancient Sumerians with modern cesium atomic clocks that now define the unit of a second. It may seem a daunting task, but it can be done.

The Ancient Sumerians who settled down in the Middle East (Mesopotamia) from following the herds and hunting with stone spearpoints, to invent agriculture, mathematics, writing, government, and metallurgy, did so almost overnight on an archaeological timescale and it has been a mystery of archaeology just what caused this to happen.

Apparently, in their writing, cuneiform, which presses symbols into clay tablets with a stylus, the Sumerians say they got their knowledge from “the Anunaki, those who came from above”. According to Zecharia Sitchin, the word Nephilim in the Bible came from the Sumerians. Even mainstream archaeology today says that the stories of the Bible had their origins in Sumerian stories. Nephilim is Hebrew for “Those who came from above”, but it is translated as giants. I asked a yiddish scholar why this is and he said it is because those who came from above were giants.

Moving on, with the unearthing by archaeologists of the Assyrian civilization in current day Iraq, and discovery of the palace and library of King Assurbanipal in Nineveh, we now had access to some 30,000 Sumerian cuneiform tablets. Some of what was in them years later found their way to NASA scientist, Maurice Chatelain, who oversaw the communications systems of the Apollo missions to the Moon.

The language of Sumerian was decoded in 1846 by an Englishman, Henry Rawlinson, using tablets with the same text inscribed in three different languages, thus breaking the code. In 1872 they were finally translated by the English Assyriologist, George Smith. Chatelain writes in his book “Our Cosmic Ancestors”:

Among the tablets translated by Smith was a certain quantity that contained nothing but numbers, fantastically huge numbers, apparently derived from complicated calculations...

I have not been able to find out to this day when and where somebody decided to study these mathematical tablets again, but the translation into our decimal system was finally published a few years ago, and one number stood out. It consisted of fifteen digits: 195,995,200,000,000...

I personally discovered the existence of the number in 1955,...

One day I remembered that the Sumerians, who were the ancestors of the Babylonians, who were in turn invaded by the Assyrians, used calculations based on multiples of 60 more than 3,000 years ago. We still do not know for sure who the Sumerians were and where they came from but we have found out that they were truly great astronomers who knew the revolution periods of all the planets of the solar system, including Uranus and Neptune...

They were the ones who divided the day into 86,400 seconds with 24 hours of 60 minutes of 60 seconds each. Immediately the realization came to me that the number of Nineveh represented a very, very long long period of time expressed in seconds!...

The thought flashed into my mind that the clever Sumerians were familiar, among other things astronomical, with the precession of the equinoxes — the turning of the terrestrial axis of rotation around the pole of the ecliptic. This movement has a cycle of 9.540 million days or about 26,000 years.

...When I divided the Nineveh number by the cycle of the precession of the equinoxes, also called The Big Year, I had the greatest surprise of my life! The sacred number of Nineveh divided exactly into 240 Big Years of 9.450 million days each...

Then came my conclusion that this enormous number of Nineveh could very well be the long lost magic number called the 'great constant of the solar system' the number that alchemists, astrologers, and astronomers had been looking for for a very long time, while their ancestors were familiar with it more than 3,000 years ago...

To put it short, Chatelain tested this and found the Nineveh constant was exact multiples of the conjunction periods of all the planets.

This constant was the number I needed to suggest that the Ancient Sumerians got the unit of a second, which came from their sexagesimal counting system, from extraterrestrials. I suggest extraterrestrials, because the second I find is a base unit that describes a quantum mechanical solution of the solar system and the atom's proton in common, as in the equations presented at the beginning of this paper. In other words, the second might not be arbitrary, but a natural constant. I can suggest this because we now define the second not with dividing up the rotation period of the Earth, but with cesium atomic clocks, which started in 1967 the year Canada's most famous and well documented UFO landing was sighted, and that was sighted in one of the only reserves of the rare element cesium that makes atomic clocks possible.

Here is how we do it. The Nineveh constant is 1.959552E14 seconds/cycle. The second is now defined as 9,192,631,770 cycles of the cesium atom per second. We have

$$\frac{\text{NinevehConstant}}{\text{CesiumOscillations}} = \frac{1.959552E14}{9,192,631,770} = 21,316.5507 \frac{\text{sec}^2}{\text{cycle}^2}$$

$$\sqrt{21,316.5507 \frac{\text{sec}^2}{\text{cycle}^2}} = 146.0018855 \frac{\text{sec}}{\text{cycle}} \approx 146 \frac{\text{sec}}{\text{cycle}}$$

A day has 86,400 seconds:

$$\left(86,400 \frac{\text{sec}}{\text{day}}\right) \left(\frac{\text{cycle}}{146 \text{sec}}\right) = 591.7808 \frac{\text{cycle}}{\text{day}} \approx 592 \frac{\text{cycle}}{\text{day}}$$

A year is 365.25 days, but this is a cycle of the Earth around the Sun so we have:

$$\frac{592 \frac{\text{cycle}}{\text{day}}}{365.25 \frac{\text{day}}{\text{cycle}}} = 1.62 \frac{\text{cycle}^2}{\text{day}^2} \approx 1.618 = \Phi \frac{\text{cycle}^2}{\text{day}^2}$$

It is the golden ratio. But we have to take the square root to get the right units. A particular approximation we have to Φ is found in Ancient Egypt. While the Sumerians started civilization that spread throughout the world, the Ancient Egyptians did the same at the same time independently, but they were isolated by ocean mountains and desert so no one invaded them, like Semitic tribes with the Sumerians. However, they did much similar to the Sumerians, like dividing the day into 12 hours as well. And, there has been much theorizing that Ancient Aliens gave them a great deal, like the pyramids, whose construction cannot be explained. Questions remain how such large, heavy stones were cut, moved, and stacked to make them.

In Maurice Chatelain's book "Our Cosmic Ancestors" Chatelain suggests the pyramids were landing beacons for alien craft because they were polished, and reflective, and were flat on top. But, I would like to point out when Chatelain solves the mathematical proportions of the pyramids he suggests it is because the ancient Egyptians approximated the golden ratio, Φ , above in our cesium clocks and the constant of Nineveh, as $\frac{196}{121}$ and the pi (π) the ratio of the circumference of a circle to its diameter as $\frac{22}{7}$. In the pyramids Chatelain had to reconcile Φ and π with one another, which don't reconcile except in the Egyptian approximations to these values above if we take the square root of Φ , as we have to do above with $\Phi \frac{\text{cycle}^2}{\text{day}^2}$. We have for our cesium clocks with respect to the Nineveh constant as Chatelain suggests we have for the pyramids:

$$\sqrt{\Phi} \approx \frac{4}{\pi}$$

$$\sqrt{\Phi} \approx \sqrt{\frac{196}{121}} = \frac{14}{11} = \frac{4}{\pi} = 4 \frac{7}{22} = \frac{28}{22} = \frac{14}{11}$$

So this all has to do with the number

$$\sqrt{\Phi} \approx \frac{14}{11} = 1.272727\dots$$

So the Nineveh constant that the ancient Sumerians wrote down thousands of years ago at the dawn of civilization not only describes the periodic motion of the planets, planets that during the 18th century at the birth of modern science we did not even know existed, which Maurice Chatelain said divide evenly into it to four places after the decimal, not only does it do that, it describes the oscillations of a cesium atom in its ground state that define a second, a second that I have shown in theory is a natural constant at the basis of describing the planets and the

atom in common. And, it does so via the relationship between the golden ratio and pi that the Ancient Egyptians used to construct their pyramids. In turn, this cesium, which is ideal for making such clocks was in the end used to define the second more accurately and made the standard in 1967 when one of the most well documented UFO landings was reported in detail, with much evidence to back it up, near Winnipeg, the capitol of the Manitoba province where most of the Cesium is mined for making such clocks. The Ancient Sumerians have been a mystery to archaeology, how they settled down from hunting with stone spearpoints to invent writing, mathematics, metallurgy, and agriculture. Also mysterious are the ancient Egyptians, who invented mathematics, writing and agriculture around the the same time as the ancient Sumerians independently and separately, especially their enormous stone pyramids stacked with enormous stone blocks to precise Mathematical dimensions that we cannot even figure today how they could have been cut, transported, and lifted. Did the ancient Sumerians and Egyptians get their start in inventing civilization from visitors from another world more advanced than ourselves? Can we find indications of the presence of such visitors in ancient and contemporary times, and are there clues that show them to be the same people?

I also found that UFOs are prominent in Canada, and are most abundant in the Manitoba province where the cesium is mined. In fact most of their sightings are around the capital of Manitoba, Canada Winnipeg near the cesium mines and the Falcon Lake UFO incident. A Manitoba news station did a story on it saying Manitoba is a UFO hotspot, with most of the sightings in Winnipeg, significantly. They reported the numbers of sightings in cities in Manitoba up to 2016 when the story was released. They are:

Winnipeg 767, Carman 53, Brandon 45, Thompson 40, Sperling 36

I immediately knew to look to Manitoba, Canada after I learned cesium was abundant there because Todd, who goes by the name of "Taken by the Greys", said on Canadian radio that he was abducted by grey aliens at lake Manitoba, and by a secret people in Black Suits. He said he was the one who first said there were men in black suits, and that it is from him that they got the idea for the film "Men in Black", a science fiction movie about men and women who wear black suits and oversee our relationships with extraterrestrials on Earth. Todd has a Youtube channel where he has documented his abduction at Lake Manitoba, it goes by the name of Taken by the Greys.

I have found that the basis unit of one second is not just a Natural constant for physical systems like the atom and the planets around the Sun, but for the basis of biological life, that it is in the sixfold Nature of the chemical skeletons from which life is built, the hydrocarbons.

We return to a couple of the equations at the beginning of this paper...

$$1second = \frac{1}{6\alpha^2} \cdot \frac{r_p}{m_p} \sqrt{\frac{4\pi h}{Gc}}$$

$$1second = \frac{KE_m}{KE_e}(EarthDay)$$

The first can be written:

$$14) \quad \frac{1}{\alpha^2 m_p} \sqrt{\frac{h 4\pi r_p^2}{G c}} = 6 \text{proton} \cdot \text{seconds} = \text{carbon}(C)$$

$$15) \quad \frac{1}{\alpha^2 m_p} \sqrt{\frac{h 4\pi r_p^2}{G c}} = 1 \text{proton} \cdot 6 \text{seconds} = \text{hydrogen}(H)$$

From which instead of saying the left sides of these equations are seconds, we say they are proton-seconds by not letting the units of m_p cancel with the bodies of these equations on the left, which are in units of mass, but rather divide into them, giving us a number of protons. I say this is the biological because these are the hydrocarbons the backbones of biological chemistry. We see they display sixfold symmetry. I can generate integer numbers of protons from the time values from these equations for all of the elements with a computer program. Some results are:

```
By what value would you like to increment?: 0.25
How many values would you like to calculate for t in equation? (No more than 100): 100
24.1199 protons 0.250000 second 0.119904 decpart
12.0600 protons 0.500000 second 0.059952 decpart
8.0400 protons 0.750000 second 0.039968 decpart
6.0300 protons 1.000000 second 0.029976 decpart
4.0200 protons 1.500000 second 0.019984 decpart
3.0150 protons 2.000000 second 0.014988 decpart
2.1927 protons 2.750000 second 0.192718 decpart
2.0100 protons 3.000000 second 0.009992 decpart
1.2060 protons 5.000000 second 0.205995 decpart
1.1486 protons 5.250000 second 0.148567 decpart
1.0964 protons 5.500000 second 0.096359 decpart
1.0487 protons 5.750000 second 0.048691 decpart
1.0050 protons 6.000000 second 0.004996 decpart
0.2487 protons 24.250000 second 0.248659 decpart
0.2461 protons 24.500000 second 0.246121 decpart
0.2436 protons 24.750000 second 0.243635 decpart
Program ended with exit code: 0
```

A very interesting thing here is looking at the values generated by the program, the smallest integer value 1 second produces 6 protons (carbon) and the largest integer value 6 seconds produces one proton (hydrogen). Beyond six seconds you have fractional protons, and the rest of the elements heavier than carbon are formed by fractional seconds. These are the hydrocarbons the backbones of biological chemistry. And carbon is the core element of life. We see the duration of the base unit of measuring time, 1 second, given to us by the ancients, is perfect for the mathematical formulation of life chemistry. Here is the code for the program, it finds integer solutions for time values, incremented by the program at the discretion of the user:

```

#include <stdio.h>
#include <math.h>
int main(int argc, const char * argv[]) {

    int n;
    float value=0, increment,t=0, p=1.67262E-27, h=6.62607E-34,G=6.67408E-11,
c=299792458,protons[100],r=0.833E-15;

    do
    {
        printf("By what value would you like to increment: ");
        scanf("%f", &increment);
        printf("How many values would you like to calculate for t in equation 1 (no more than 100?): ");
        scanf("%i", &n);
    }
    while (n>=101);
    {

        for (int i=0; i<n;i++)
        {
            protons[i]=((137*137)/(t*p))*sqrt(h*4*(3.14159)*(r*r)/(G*c));

            int intpart=(int)protons[i];
            float decpart=protons[i]-intpart;
            t=t+increment;
            if (decpart<0.25)
            { printf("%.4f protons %f seconds %f decpart \n", protons[i], t-increment, decpart);
            }}}
    }
}

```

The Geographic Layout For UFOs and Cesium Mines

Interestingly, a straight line south from Falcon Lake where the UFO sighting was connects with Houston, NASA's location of mission control for space flights. I thought perhaps I was looking at extraterrestrial navigation routes. The line of Falcon Lake to Houston, connects with Baja Mexico, and that with Seattle, Washington a hub of tech Industry, where Microsoft is. A square is made that encloses the United States nicely whose center is Denver, Colorado and Boulder Colorado, Denver a so-called Beta World City, which means it is a primary node in the global economic Network. Boulder Colorado maintains one of our Cesium atomic clocks that we use to keep track of time accurately for science and calendars. It is a one of a handful of laboratories that does this. See the maps and drawings below:

The green square in the south-east corner just south-east of Winnipeg is Falcon Lake, the grey circle just north of there (Just north-east of Winnipeg is Bernic Lake). They are very close to one another.

Closing Statement

We are at a time in our history when we have built telescopes that we have been able to put in space. They have enabled us to detect some of the tiny specks orbiting other stars that are planets, tiny specks that we always guessed should exist if our theory was right that planets orbiting other stars are common place. Some of these planets that we have found have turned out to be like the Earth, solid and at the right distance from their star to not be too hot for water to vaporize, or too far for it to freeze, but for it exist in its liquid phase, a condition we believe to be necessary for life to happen as we understand it.

We are further at a time in our development where we can leave the Earth and explore some of the planets orbiting our star, the Sun. Our technology in the realm of computing power, as achieved with solid state technology and integrated circuitry in our computers has taken off into beyond what we ever dreamed it would reach so early on. It has enabled us make robotic landers and send them to Mars to send back information about its terrain, whether it has water and can be colonized, a necessity for us to do because resources on Earth are finite, and our survival in the end depends on us being able to expand out into space.

But these are interplanetary missions, and in the end we need to travel between the stars. While the planets orbiting our Sun are accessible — it takes about a year with current technology to get to Mars — the distances between the stars are immense, with current technology it would take thousands of years to reach the nearest one. Space is inhospitable: its is cold and devoid of air, it is a major undertaking just to leave the Earth and go to the Moon that takes months of planning; we can't just press a button and take off and go there at anytime we wish.

But computers are not just making developments in the physical and biological sciences, giving us an idea of our origins, where we going, and what we are about, they are making advancements in our ability to engineer better ones of them, themselves; the ability to make more complex computations quicker and store information in smaller and smaller volumes. With such computing power we may be able to develop a way to not just travel to the planets of our star system, but to travel to the planets of other star systems.

This I believe is important to do. Especially in light of this study. Because, through it, we see the solar system and the atom have a profound structure mathematically that is interconnected, and we have to ask, why our solar system has this apparent design, and the Earth has such favorable conditions to support life over the billions of years needed for life to develop into something as sophisticated as the human, that can alter its environment in its favor to such a degree that no other animal has ever achieved.

We have to ask if this is not just true of our star system, but of other star systems; there are many kinds of stars, big hot ones, and small cool ones. If our solar system in its mathematical structure reveals so much about us, what does the mathematical structure of other star systems reveal about the inhabitants of their planets? Are the different star systems related but different, and if so what would that tell us about our purpose in life, or its meaning?

In order to to make the jump to the stars, we have to undergo an expansion of consciousness to adapt to space travel and its implications. It may be we will soon find that there is already a social structure for the different worlds in common that allows for the different space faring civilizations to function together, and that Earth might be invited to join such an intergalactic community. I leave this paraphrasing a poem by the astronomer Carl Sagan:

The surface of the Earth is the shore of cosmic ocean
From it we have learned most of what we know
Some part of our being knows this is from where we came
Recently, we have waded out to sea, enough to wet our toes
Some part of our being knows this is from where we came
We long to return
These aspirations, I think, are not irreverent
Though they may trouble whatever Gods may be.

It would seem Manitoba UFO activity is happening again in the same areas as the falcon lake incident and near the cesium mines. The following video shows compelling footage:

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Ykg_aNVxYAO

Part 3: Biological Life Part of a Universal Natural Process In The Universe

Introduction I have a theory for the star systems, the planets and their suns, wherein such systems are solved with the Schrödinger wave equation that is used to solve atomic systems. The result is that star systems and atomic systems, systems on the macro scales and micro scales, are governed by the same underlying principles. It came to pass that this theory indicated an overlap with biological systems indicating that biological life could be part of the same idea, and that is what I hope to pull out of that paper and develop here.

The theory for the planets, which also predicted the radius of a proton, which is one of the fundamental particles out of which matter is made, suggested that star systems which support life are a part of a Universal natural process. One of the conditions for star systems that support life made use of the interesting fact that has mystified science for some time now, that the Moon is the right size and distance from the Earth that it nearly perfectly eclipses the Sun. The reason a moon would be necessary for life to be optimally successful on a habitable planet is that we know our moon that orbits our Earth, makes life here successful because it holds the Earth at its inclination to its orbit around the Sun allowing for the seasons, thus preventing extreme hot and extreme cold.

Interestingly, the solution for the planets of the Schrödinger wave equation, was quantized in terms of the Earth's moon, and a base unit of one second. The Moon seems to be some sort of a natural yardstick. The strange thing is that the basis unit of time is one second and the second was not developed with the planets and atoms in mind, so it is strange that it lands upon the function of a natural constant in our theory. In the theory (*An Abstract Theory of Reality*, *Beardsley 2024*) I talk a little about why that might be. The second came to us from the Ancient Sumerians, who invented civilization with settling down from following the herds and hunting with stone spearpoint to invent agriculture, metallurgy, writing, and mathematics. They had a base 60 counting system, and found it convenient then to divide the Earth day (rotation period) into 24 hours, which in the end became adopted by the world. Their base 60 counting resulted in the Babylonians dividing the hour into 60 minutes, and that in turn into 60 seconds, and that is how we have the duration of a second we have today. They chose base 60 (sexagesimal) because 60 is evenly divisible by so much from which they gave us the 12 hour day and 12 hour night or 24 hour day from sunrise to sunrise, sunset to sunset. 12 times 5 is 60, also 60 times 6 is 360, they gave us the 360 degree circle as well.

In this paper I show that the same unit of a second that describes planetary systems and atomic system in common describes hydrocarbons, the skeletons of biological life chemistry. I further show that it predicts the atomic radii of the hydrogen and carbon atoms from which such skeletons are made. Hydrogen and carbon are the most abundant elements in life chemistry, carbon is the core element upon which life is made, and hydrogen is the simplest element, element one in the periodic table of the elements, consisting of 1 proton, and is the most abundant element in the universe by far, and plays the dominant role in all of chemistry.

A Theory For Biological Hydrocarbons I have found that the basis unit of one second is not just a Natural constant for physical systems like the atom and the planets around the Sun (See my paper *An Abstract Theory of Reality, Beardsley 2024*) but for the basis of biological life, that it is in the sixfold Nature of the chemical skeletons from which life is built, the hydrocarbons. I found

$$1). \quad 1second = \frac{1}{6\alpha^2} \cdot \frac{r_p}{m_p} \sqrt{\frac{4\pi h}{Gc}}$$

$$2). \quad 1second = \frac{KE_m}{KE_e}(EarthDay)$$

Where $\alpha = 1/137$ is the fine structure constant, r_p is the radius of a proton, m_p is the mass of a proton, h is Planck's constant, G is the constant of gravitation, c is the speed of light, KE_m is the kinetic energy of the Moon, KE_e is the kinetic energy of the Earth, and *EarthDay* is the rotation period of the Earth is one day.

The first can be written:

$$3). \quad \frac{1}{\alpha^2 m_p} \sqrt{\frac{h 4\pi r_p^2}{Gc}} = 6proton \cdot seconds = carbon(C)$$

$$4). \quad \frac{1}{\alpha^2 m_p} \sqrt{\frac{h 4\pi r_p^2}{Gc}} = 1proton \cdot 6seconds = hydrogen(H)$$

From which instead of saying the left sides of these equations are seconds, we say they are proton-seconds by not letting the units of m_p cancel with the bodies of these equations on the left, which are in units of mass, but rather divide into them, giving us a number of protons. I say this is the biological because these are the hydrocarbons the backbones of biological chemistry. We see they display sixfold symmetry. I can generate integer numbers of protons from the time values from these equations for all of the elements with a computer program. Some results are:

```
By what value would you like to increment?: 0.25
How many values would you like to calculate for t in equation? (No more than 100): 100
24.1199 protons 0.250000 second 0.119904 decpart
12.0600 protons 0.500000 second 0.059952 decpart
8.0400 protons 0.750000 second 0.039968 decpart
6.0300 protons 1.000000 second 0.029976 decpart
4.0200 protons 1.500000 second 0.019984 decpart
3.0150 protons 2.000000 second 0.014988 decpart
2.1927 protons 2.750000 second 0.192718 decpart
2.0100 protons 3.000000 second 0.009992 decpart
1.2060 protons 5.000000 second 0.205995 decpart
1.1486 protons 5.250000 second 0.148567 decpart
1.0964 protons 5.500000 second 0.096359 decpart
1.0487 protons 5.750000 second 0.048691 decpart
1.0050 protons 6.000000 second 0.004996 decpart
0.2487 protons 24.250000 second 0.248659 decpart
0.2461 protons 24.500000 second 0.246121 decpart
0.2436 protons 24.750000 second 0.243635 decpart
Program ended with exit code: 0
```

A very interesting thing here is looking at the values generated by the program, the smallest integer value 1 second produces 6 protons (carbon) and the largest integer value 6 seconds produces one proton (hydrogen). Beyond six seconds you have fractional protons, and the rest of the elements heavier than carbon are formed by fractional seconds. These are the hydrocarbons the backbones of biological chemistry. And carbon is the core element of life. We see the duration of the base unit of measuring time, 1 second, given to us by the ancients (the base 60, sexagesimal, system of counting of the Sumerians who invented math and writing and started civilization), is perfect for the mathematical formulation of life chemistry. Here is the code for the program, it finds integer solutions for time values, incremented by the program at the discretion of the user:

```
#include <stdio.h>
#include <math.h>
int main(int argc, const char * argv[]) {

    int n;
    float value=0, increment,t=0, p=1.67262E-27, h=6.62607E-34,G=6.67408E-11,
    c=299792458,protons[100],r=0.833E-15;

    do
    {
        printf("By what value would you like to increment?: ");
        scanf("%f", &increment);
        printf("How many values would you like to calculate for t in equation 1 (no more than 100?): ");
        scanf("%i", &n);
    }
    while (n>=101);
    {

        for (int i=0; i<n;i++)
        {
            protons[i]=((137*137)/(t*p))*sqrt(h*4*(3.14159)*(r*r)/(G*c));

            int intpart=(int)protons[i];
            float decpart=protons[i]-intpart;
            t=t+increment;
            if (decpart<0.25)
            { printf("%.4f protons %f seconds %f decpart \n", protons[i], t-increment, decpart);
              }
            }
        }
    }
```

We have that

$$\frac{1}{\alpha^2} \cdot \frac{r_p}{m_p} \sqrt{\frac{4\pi\hbar}{Gc}} = 18769 \frac{0.833E-15}{1.67262E-27} \sqrt{\frac{4\pi(6.62607E-34)}{(6.67408E-11)(299,792458)}} = 6.029978s \approx 6s$$

Since this 6 seconds is also proton-seconds we have

$$5). \quad \frac{1}{6_{protons}} \cdot \frac{1}{\alpha^2} \cdot \frac{r_p}{m_p} \sqrt{\frac{4\pi\hbar}{Gc}} = 1second \text{ is carbon (C)}$$

$$6). \quad \frac{1}{1_{proton}} \cdot \frac{1}{\alpha^2} \cdot \frac{r_p}{m_p} \sqrt{\frac{4\pi\hbar}{Gc}} = 6seconds \text{ is hydrogen (H)}$$

Our Theory For Hydrocarbons With all that has been said we are equipped to proceed. We want to consider the radius of a hydrogen atom and the radius of a carbon atom. The radius of a carbon atom given in your periodic table of the elements is often 70 to 76 picometers. The covalent radius of hydrogen is given as 31 picometers. The atomic radius of hydrogen is 53 picometers and the atomic radius of carbon is 67 picometers. We want to consider the atomic radii of both, because the covalent radius, determined by x-ray diffraction for diatomic hydrogen, is the size of two hydrogen atoms joined H₂ divided by two, where it is measured that way, joined, in the laboratory. Carbon is C₂ divided by 2. We are interested in the single carbon and hydrogen atoms, because we want to know what our theory for their six-fold symmetry with one another in their representations in proton-seconds says about the way they combine as the skeletons of life chemistry. We start with the Planck constant, h , which is like flux, a mass (perhaps a number of particles) per second over an area. That is it is kilograms per second over square area:

$$h = 6.62607E - 34 J \cdot s = 6.62607E - 37 \frac{kg}{s} \cdot m^2$$

We have equations 1 and 2:

$$1). \quad \frac{1}{6 \text{ protons}} \cdot \frac{1}{\alpha^2} \cdot \frac{r_p}{m_p} \sqrt{\frac{4\pi h}{Gc}} = 1 \text{ second is carbon (C)}$$

$$2). \quad \frac{1}{1 \text{ proton}} \cdot \frac{1}{\alpha^2} \cdot \frac{r_p}{m_p} \sqrt{\frac{4\pi h}{Gc}} = 6 \text{ seconds is hydrogen (H)}$$

We can write these

$$\left(6.62607E - 37 \frac{kg}{s} \cdot m^2 \right) \frac{6 \text{ seconds}}{m_p} =$$

$$3). \quad \left(6.62607E - 37 \frac{kg}{s} \cdot m^2 \right) \frac{6 \text{ seconds}}{1.67262E - 27 kg} = 2.37689E - 6 m^2$$

$$\left(6.62607E - 37 \frac{kg}{s} \cdot m^2 \right) \frac{1 \text{ second}}{6 m_p} =$$

$$4). \quad \left(6.62607E - 37 \frac{kg}{s} \cdot m^2 \right) \frac{1 \text{ second}}{6(1.67262E - 27 kg)} = 6.602486E - 8 m^2$$

We have from 3 and 4...

$$5). \quad \frac{\frac{h}{m_p} \cdot \frac{(6 \text{ seconds})}{1}}{\frac{h}{m_p} \cdot \frac{(1 \text{ second})}{6}} = \frac{2.37689E - 6 m^2}{6.602486E - 8 m^2} = 35.9999 \approx 40$$

We find the ratio between the surface areas of the hydrogen and carbon atoms:

$$6). \quad H_{surface} = 4\pi(r_H^2) = 3.52989E - 20m^2$$

$$7). \quad C_{surface} = 4\pi(r_C^2) = 5.64104E - 20m^2$$

$$\frac{4\pi(53pm)^2}{4\pi(67pm)^2} = 0.62575 \approx 0.618... = \phi$$

It is the golden mean. These atomic radii are the radii between the nucleus of the atoms and their valence shell, which is what we want because the valence shell is the outermost electrons responsible for the way the hydrogen and the carbon combine to make hydrocarbons. We will write this

$$8). \quad \frac{r_H^2}{r_C^2} = \phi_{HC}$$

I am guessing the reason we have the golden mean here is that it is the number used for closest packing. But what we really want to do is look at the concept of action, for hydrogen given by six seconds and carbon given by 1 second. We take equations 1 and 2:

$$1). \quad \frac{1}{6protons} \cdot \frac{1}{\alpha^2} \cdot \frac{r_p}{m_p} \sqrt{\frac{4\pi h}{Gc}} = 1second \text{ is carbon (C)}$$

$$2). \quad \frac{1}{1proton} \cdot \frac{1}{\alpha^2} \cdot \frac{r_p}{m_p} \sqrt{\frac{4\pi h}{Gc}} = 6seconds \text{ is hydrogen (H)}$$

And, we write

$$9). \quad m_p \sqrt{\frac{Gc}{h}} \int_0^t dt = r_A$$

Where r_A is the radius of the atom, and t its time values given here by equations 1 and 2. We have for hydrogen

$$10). \quad m_p \sqrt{\frac{Gc}{h}} \int_0^t dt = (1.67262E - 27kg) \sqrt{\frac{(6.67408E - 11)(299,792,458)}{6.62607E - 34}} \int_0^{6sec} dt$$

$$=(9.2E - 12m/s)(6seconds) = 5.5E - 11m$$

This is actually very close to the radius of a hydrogen which can vary around this depending on how you are looking at it, which we said is given by 5.3E-11m. For carbon we have:

$$11). \quad m_p \sqrt{\frac{Gc}{h}} \int_0^t dt = (1.67262E - 27kg) \sqrt{\frac{(6.67408E - 11)(299,792,458)}{6.62607E - 34}} \int_0^{6sec+1sec} dt$$

$$=(9.2E - 12m/s)(7seconds) = 6.44E - 11m$$

And this is actually very close to the radius of a carbon atom which is 6.7E-11m. The thing is if we consider the bond length of the simplest hydrocarbon CH₄, methane, which can be thought of as

$$16). \quad r_H + r_C = 5.3E - 11m + 6.7E - 11m = 1.2E - 10m$$

our, equations give

$$17). \quad r_H + r_C = 5.5E - 11m + 6.44E - 11m = 1.2E - 10m$$

which are the same thing. Thus we have the basis for a theory of everything in that it includes the macro scale, the Earth/Moon/Sun System, because we had:

$$1second = \frac{KE_m}{KE_e}(EarthDay)$$

and it includes the radius of the proton which is the radius and mass of a proton and gives 1 second

$$1second = \frac{1}{6\alpha^2} \cdot \frac{r_p}{m_p} \sqrt{\frac{4\pi h}{Gc}}$$

and we have the hydrocarbons the skeleton of the chemistry of life give one second

$$1). \quad \frac{1}{6protons} \cdot \frac{1}{\alpha^2} \cdot \frac{r_p}{m_p} \sqrt{\frac{4\pi h}{Gc}} = 1second \text{ is carbon (C)}$$

$$2). \quad \frac{1}{1proton} \cdot \frac{1}{\alpha^2} \cdot \frac{r_p}{m_p} \sqrt{\frac{4\pi h}{Gc}} = 6seconds \text{ is hydrogen (H)}$$

and because they predict the radii of the carbon and hydrogen atoms at the core of life

$$10). \quad m_p \sqrt{\frac{Gc}{h}} \int_0^t dt = (1.67262E - 27kg) \sqrt{\frac{(6.67408E - 11)(299,792,458)}{6.62607E - 34}} \int_0^{6sec} dt$$

$$=(9.2E - 12m/s)(6seconds) = 5.5E - 11m$$

$$11). \quad m_p \sqrt{\frac{Gc}{h}} \int_0^t dt = (1.67262E - 27kg) \sqrt{\frac{(6.67408E - 11)(299,792,458)}{6.62607E - 34}} \int_0^{6sec+1sec} dt$$

$$=(9.2E - 12m/s)(7seconds) = 6.44E - 11m$$

Part 4: The Solar Formulation For The Solution Of The Wave Equation

The Solar Formulation

Our solution of the wave equation for the planets gives the kinetic energy of the Earth from the mass of the Moon orbiting the Earth, but you could formulate based on the Earth orbiting the Sun. In our lunar formulation we had:

$$1. \quad KE_e = \sqrt{3} \frac{R_\odot}{R_m} \cdot \frac{G^2 M_e^2 M_m^3}{2 \hbar_\odot^2}$$

We remember the Moon perfectly eclipses the Sun which is to say

$$2. \quad \frac{R_\odot}{R_m} = \frac{r_e}{r_m}$$

Thus equation 1 becomes

$$3. \quad KE_e = \sqrt{3} \frac{r_e}{r_m} \cdot \frac{G^2 M_e^2 M_m^3}{2 \hbar_\odot^2}$$

The kinetic energy of the Earth is

$$4. \quad KE_e = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \frac{GM_\odot M_e}{r_e}$$

Putting this in equation 3 gives the mass of the Sun:

$$5. \quad M_\odot = \sqrt{3} r_e^2 \cdot \frac{GM_e}{r_m} \cdot \frac{M_m^3}{\hbar_\odot^2}$$

We recognize that the orbital velocity of the Moon is

$$6. \quad v_m^2 = \frac{GM_e}{r_m}$$

So equation 5 becomes

$$7. \quad M_\odot = \sqrt{3} r_e^2 \cdot v_m^2 \cdot \frac{M_m^3}{\hbar_\odot^2}$$

This gives the mass of the Moon is

$$8. \quad M_m^3 = \frac{M_\odot \hbar_\odot^2}{\sqrt{3} r_e^2 v_m^2}$$

Putting this in equation 1 yields

$$9. \quad KE_e = \frac{R_\odot}{R_m} \cdot \frac{G^2 M_e^2 M_\odot}{2 r_e^2 v_m^2}$$

We now multiply through by M_e^2/M_e^2 and we have

$$10. \quad KE_e = \frac{R_\odot}{R_m} \cdot \frac{G^2 M_e^4 M_\odot}{2r_e^2 v_m^2 M_e^2}$$

Thus the Planck constant for the Sun, \hbar_\odot , in this case the star is the Sun, is angular momentum quantized, the angular momentum we will call L_p , the subscript p for Planck. We have

$$L_p = r_e v_m M_e = r_e v_m M_e = (1.496E11m)(1022m/s)(5.972E24kg) = 9.13E38kg \cdot \frac{m^2}{s}$$

$$L_p^2 = r_e^2 v_m^2 M_e^2 = 7.4483E77J \cdot m^2 \cdot kg = 8.3367E77kg^2 \cdot \frac{m^4}{s^2}$$

We write for the solution of the Earth/Sun system:

$$11. \quad KE_e = \frac{R_\odot}{R_m} \cdot \frac{G^2 M_e^4 M_\odot}{2L_p^2}$$

Let us compare this to that of an atom:

$$12. \quad E = -\frac{Z^2}{n^2} \cdot \frac{k_e^2 e^4 m_e}{2\hbar^2}$$

We notice that in equation 11

$$\frac{Z^2}{n^2} \rightarrow \frac{R_\odot}{R_m}; \quad k_e^2 \rightarrow G^2; \quad e^4 \rightarrow M_e^4; \quad m_e \rightarrow M_\odot; \quad \hbar^2 \rightarrow L_p^2$$

L_p is really \hbar_\odot . We can write 11 as

$$13. \quad KE_e = \frac{R_\odot}{R_m} \cdot \frac{G^2 M_e^4 M_\odot}{2\hbar_\odot^2}$$

We say. $\hbar_\odot = \hbar_\odot/2\pi$. That is

$$\hbar_\odot = 9.13E38J \cdot s$$

$$h_\odot = 2\pi\hbar_\odot = 5.7365E39J \cdot s$$

Let us see how accurate our equation is:

$$KE_e = \frac{R_\odot}{R_m} \cdot \frac{G^2 M_e^4 M_\odot}{2\hbar_\odot^2}$$

$$= \frac{R_{\odot} (6.67408E - 11)^2 (5.972E24kg)^4 (1.9891E30kg)}{R_m \cdot 2(8.3367E77kg^2 \cdot \frac{m^4}{s^2})}$$

$$= \frac{R_{\odot}}{R_m} (6.759E30J)$$

$$\frac{R_{\odot}}{R_m} = \frac{6.957E8m}{1737400m} = 400.426$$

$$KE_e = 2.70655E33J$$

We have that the kinetic energy of the Earth is

$$KE_{earth} = \frac{1}{2} (5.972E24kg) (30,290m/s)^2 = 2.7396E33J$$

Our equation has an accuracy of

$$\frac{2.70655E33J}{2.7396E33J} = 98.79 \%$$

Which is very good.

We call L_p the same \hbar_{\odot} in our solar solution. But we now want our r_n solution for the solar formulation. M_e is the mass of the Earth and M_{\odot} is the mass of the Sun. We have our solution might be

$$14. \quad r_n = \frac{\hbar_{\odot}^2}{GM_e^3} \cdot \frac{R_m}{R_{\odot}}$$

Where \hbar_{\odot} is

$$\hbar_{\odot} = 9.13E38J \cdot s$$

We have

$$15. \quad r_3 = \frac{(9.13E38)^2}{(6.67408E - 11)(5.972E24kg)^3} \cdot \frac{1}{400.5986} = 1.4638E11m$$

This has an accuracy of

$$\frac{1.4638E11m}{1.496E11m} 100 = 97.85 \%$$

Thus the solutions to the wave equation

$$-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \left[\frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r^2 \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \right) + \frac{1}{r^2 \sin \theta} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \left(\sin \theta \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \right) + \frac{1}{r^2 \sin^2 \theta} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \phi^2} \right] \psi + V(r)\psi = E\psi$$

for the solar formulations are

$$13) \quad KE_e = \frac{R_\odot}{R_m} \cdot \frac{G^2 M_e^4 M_\odot}{2\hbar_\odot^2}$$

$$14) \quad r_n = \frac{\hbar_\odot^2}{GM_e^3} \cdot \frac{R_m}{R_\odot}$$

$$\hbar_\odot = 9.13E38J \cdot s$$

$$h_\odot = 2\pi\hbar_\odot = 5.7365E39J \cdot s$$

Equating The Lunar And Solar Formulations Yield Our 1 Second Base Unit

Let us equate equation 1 with equation 13:

$$1. \quad KE_e = \sqrt{n} \frac{R_\odot}{R_m} \cdot \frac{G^2 M_e^2 M_m^3}{2\hbar_\odot^2}$$

$$13. \quad KE_e = \frac{R_\odot}{R_m} \cdot \frac{G^2 M_e^4 M_\odot}{2\hbar_\odot^2}$$

$$\sqrt{3} \frac{R_\odot}{R_m} \cdot \frac{G^2 M_e^2 M_m^3}{2\hbar_\odot^2} = \frac{R_\odot}{R_m} \cdot \frac{G^2 M_e^4 M_\odot}{2L_p^2}$$

This gives:

$$16. \quad L_p = \sqrt{\frac{M_e^2 M_\odot}{M_m^3 \sqrt{3}}} \cdot \hbar_\odot$$

We remember that

$$\hbar_\odot = (hC)KE_p$$

$$hC = 1second$$

$$C = \frac{1}{3} \cdot \frac{1}{\alpha^2 c} \sqrt{\frac{1}{3} \cdot \frac{2\pi r_p}{Gm_p^3}}$$

$$\frac{1}{6\alpha^2 m_p} \sqrt{\frac{h4\pi r_p^2}{Gc}} = 1.004996352 \text{seconds}$$

This gives

$$17. \quad r_e v_m M_e = \frac{1}{6\alpha^2} \cdot \frac{r_p}{m_p} \sqrt{\frac{h4\pi}{Gc}} \cdot \frac{1}{2} M_e v_e^2 \cdot \sqrt{\frac{M_e^2 M_\odot}{M_m^3 \sqrt{3}}}$$

We have

$$18. \quad 2v_m = \frac{v_e^2}{r_e} (1 \text{second}) \sqrt{\frac{M_e^2 M_\odot}{M_m^3 \sqrt{3}}}$$

This equates the orbital velocity of the Moon with the centripetal acceleration of the Earth in terms of one second by way of the mass of the Earth, the mass of the Sun, the mass of the Moon, and the orbital number of the Earth. Let us compute

$$19. \quad \sqrt{\frac{M_e^2 M_\odot}{M_m^3 \sqrt{3}}} = \sqrt{\frac{(5.972E24 \text{kg})^2 (1.9891E30 \text{kg})}{(7.34763E22 \text{kg})^3 (1.732)}} = 321,331.459 \approx 321,331$$

Let us see how well equation 18 works. v_m at aphelion is 966 m/s and $v_e = 29,800 \text{m/s}$. $r_e = 1AU = 1.496E11 \text{m}$. We have

$$2(966 \text{m/s}) = \frac{(29,800 \text{m/s})^2}{1.496E11 \text{m}} (1 \text{sec}) (321,331.459)$$

$$1,907 \text{m/s} = 1,932 \text{m/s}$$

That is an accuracy of

$$\frac{1907}{1932} = 98.7 \%$$

Equation 18 can be written:

$$20. \quad 1 \text{second} = 2r_e \frac{v_m}{v_e^2} \sqrt{\frac{M_m^3 \sqrt{3}}{M_e^2 M_\odot}}$$

From our equation:

$$\frac{1}{6\alpha^2 m_p} \sqrt{\frac{h4\pi r_p^2}{Gc}} = 1.004996352 \text{seconds}$$

We have

$$21. \quad \frac{1}{6\alpha^2} \cdot \frac{r_p}{m_p} \sqrt{\frac{h4\pi}{Gc}} = 2r_e \frac{v_m}{v_e^2} \cdot \sqrt{\frac{M_m^3 \sqrt{3}}{M_e^2 M_\odot}}$$

Since $2r_e = d_e$, the diameter of the Earth orbit, we have

$$22. \quad \frac{1}{6\alpha^2} \cdot \frac{r_p}{m_p} \sqrt{\frac{h4\pi}{Gc}} = d_e \frac{v_m}{v_e^2} \cdot \sqrt{\frac{M_m^3 \sqrt{3}}{M_e^2 M_\odot}}$$

And we see the Earth/Moon/Sun system determines the radius and mass of the proton and vice versa. We basically have

$$1second = 2v_m \frac{r_e}{v_e^2} \sqrt{\frac{M_m^3 \sqrt{3}}{M_e^2 M_\odot}}$$

$$1second = \frac{KE_{moon}}{KE_{earth}} EarthDay$$

$$1second = \frac{M_m v_m^2}{M_e v_m^2} EarthDay$$

$$23. \quad 62) \quad EarthDay = \frac{2r_e}{v_m} \sqrt{\frac{M_m}{M_\odot} \sqrt{n}}$$

Where $n = 3$ is the Earth orbital number. We have

$$EarthDay = \frac{2(1.496E11m)}{966m/s} \sqrt{\frac{7.34763E22kg}{1.9891E30kg} 1.732}$$

$$= 7.83436E4seconds$$

EarthDay=(24)(60)(60)=86400 seconds,

$$\frac{7.834E4s}{86,400s} 100 = 90.675 \% \text{ accuracy}$$

This last equation, equation 62, we can use to find the rotation period, or the length of the day, of an earth-like planet in the habitable zone of any star system, so it would be very useful.

We want to turn our attention to equation 20 and write it

$$24. \quad 1second = d_e \frac{v_m}{v_e^2} \sqrt{\frac{M_m^3 \sqrt{3}}{M_e^2 M_\odot}}$$

We see equating solar and lunar formulations for energy yield the base unit of one second.

Equating the lunar and solar solutions for orbitals instead of the for energies, which we just did, we have

$$\frac{2\hbar_\odot^2}{GM_m^3} \cdot \frac{R_\odot}{R_m} \cdot \frac{1}{\sqrt{n}} = \frac{L_p^2}{GM_e^3} \cdot \frac{R_m}{R_\odot}$$

Yields

$$25. \quad \hbar_\odot^2 \frac{M_e^3}{M_m^3} = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} L_p^2 \frac{R_m^2}{R_\odot^2}$$

Where $\sqrt{3}/2 = \cos(\pi/6)$. The accuracy of this is

$$(2.8314E33)^2 \frac{(5.972E24)^3}{(7.34763E22)^3} = (0.866)(9.13E38)^2 \frac{(1737400)^2}{(6.96E8)^2}$$

$$4.29059E72 = 4.5005E72$$

$$\frac{4.29059E72}{4.5005E72} 100 = 95.3 \%$$

Thus the energy equations gave the equation 55:

$$16. \quad L_p = \sqrt{\frac{M_e^2 M_\odot}{M_m^3 \sqrt{3}}} \cdot \hbar_\odot$$

And equating the orbital equations gives

$$26. \quad L_p^2 = \frac{2\sqrt{3}}{3} \cdot \frac{M_e^3 R_\odot^2}{M_m^3 R_m^2} \cdot \hbar_\odot^2$$

These last two yield

$$27. \quad \sqrt{2} \frac{R_\odot}{R_m} \sqrt{\frac{M_e}{M_\odot}} = 1$$

The accuracy is

$$(400.5986) \sqrt{\frac{5.972E24kg}{1.9891E30kg}} = 1$$

$$0.98 = 1$$

Is 98% accuracy. The important thing that comes out of this is our base unit of a second because we see it is also a function lunar, solar, and earth masses.

$$24. \quad 1second = d_e \frac{v_m}{v_e^2} \sqrt{\frac{M_m^3 \sqrt{3}}{M_e^2 M_\odot}}$$

Part 5: Wave Solutions For Jupiter And Saturn

Solutions For Jupiter And Saturn

We have the solution for the Bohr hydrogen atom is

$$1 \quad E = - \frac{Z^2(k_e e^2)^2 m_e}{2\hbar^2 n^2}$$

Z is the atomic number, the number of protons orbited, but for our system it is 1, because one body is orbited. n is the orbit number, which we will deal with later. We have our solution for the Earth/Moon/Sun system is

$$2 \quad E = \frac{G^2 M^2 m^3}{2h_{\odot}^2 n^2}$$

Let $M = M_e$ is the earth mass, $m = M_m$ is the lunar mass, and $h_{\odot} = 2.8314E33J \cdot s$ is our Planck constant for the Earth/Moon/Sun system. We compute equation 2:

$$E = \frac{(6.67408E-11)^2(5.972E24kg)^2(7.347673E22kg)^3}{2(2.8314E33)^2 n^2} =$$

$$\frac{3.93E30Joules}{n^2}$$

The kinetic energy of the Earth is

$$KE_e = \frac{1}{2}(5.972E24kg)(30,290m/s)^2 = 2.7396E33J$$

This is $1/n^2 = 697$

The Moon perfectly eclipses the Sun which means as seen from the Earth the Moon appears to be the same size as the Sun. This is because

$$3 \quad \frac{r_e}{r_m} \approx \frac{R_{\odot}}{R_m}$$

Where r_e is the Earth orbital distance, r_m is the Moon's orbital distance, R_{\odot} is the Sun's radius, and R_m is the Moon's radius. This is because though the Moon is 400 times further from the Sun than it is from the Earth, the Sun is 400 times larger than the Moon. That is

$$\frac{6.96E8m}{1737400m} = 400.5986$$

Thus

$$4 \quad \frac{R_{\odot}}{R_m} = 400$$

We find the quantum mechanical solution to the Earth/Moon/System is

$$5 \quad E = \sqrt{n} \frac{R_{\odot}}{R_m} \cdot \frac{G^2 M^2 m^3}{2h_{\odot}^2}$$

$n = 3$ for Earth orbit (Third Planet).

$$\sqrt{3}(400.5986)(3.93E30J) = 2.7268585E33J$$

$$\frac{2.7268585E33}{2.7396E33} = 99.5 \%$$

We see the solar Planck constant we developed works in solving the Schrödinger wave equation for the Earth/Moon/Sun system. My belief as to why this was never done is that it had to be realized that the solution of the Earth kinetic energy around the Sun as a quantum mechanical state is based on the Moon around the Earth.

Now we want to find what the wave equation solutions are for Jupiter and Saturn because they significantly carry the majority of the mass of the solar system and thus should embody most clearly the dynamics of the wave solution to the Solar System.

I find that as we cross the asteroid belt leaving behind the terrestrial planets, which are solid, and go to the gas giants and ice giants, the atomic number is no longer squared and the square root of the the orbital number moves from the numerator to the denominator. I believe this is because the solar system here should be modeled in two parts, just as it is in theories of solar system formation because there is a force other than just gravity of the Sun at work, which is the radiation pressure of the Sun, which is what separates it into two parts, the terrestrial planets on this side of the asteroid belt and the giants on the other side of the asteroid belt. The effect the radiation pressure has is to blow the lighter elements out beyond the asteroid belt when the solar system forms, which are gases such as hydrogen and helium, while the heavier elements are too heavy to be blown out from the inside of the asteroid belt, allowing for the formation of the terrestrial planets Venus, Earth, and Mars. The result is that our equation has the atomic number of the heavier metals such as calcium for the Earth, while the equation for the giants has the atomic numbers of the gasses. We write for these planets

$$6 \quad E = \frac{Z}{\sqrt{n}} \frac{G^2 M^2 m^3}{2\hbar_{\odot}^2}$$

So, for Jupiter we have (And again using the maximum orbital velocity which is at perihelion):

$$KE_j = \frac{1}{2}(1.89813E27kg)(13720m/s)^2 = 1.7865E35J$$

$$E = \frac{Z_H}{\sqrt{5}} \frac{(6.67408E-11)^2(1.89813E27kg)^2(7.347673E22kg)^3}{2(2.8314E33)^2}$$

$$E = \frac{Z_H}{\sqrt{5}}(3.971E35J) = Z_H(1.776E35J)$$

$$Z_H = \frac{1.7865E35J}{1.776E35J} = 1.006 \text{ protons} \approx 1.0 \text{ protons} = \text{hydrogen}(H)$$

Jupiter is mostly composed of hydrogen gas, and secondly helium gas, so it is appropriate that $Z = Z_H$.

Our equation for Jupiter is

$$7 \quad E = \frac{Z_H}{\sqrt{5}} \frac{G^2 M_j^2 M_m^3}{2 \hbar_{\odot}^2}$$

Where Z_H is the atomic number of hydrogen which is 1 proton, and $\sqrt{n} = \sqrt{5}$ for the orbital number of Jupiter, $n = 5$. Now we move on to Saturn...

$$KE_S = \frac{1}{2} (5.683E26kg)(10140m/s)^2 = 2.92E34J$$

$$E = \frac{Z}{\sqrt{6}} \frac{(6.67408E-11)^2 (5.683E26kg)^2 (7.347673E22)^3}{2(2.8314E33)^2}$$

$$= \frac{Z}{2.45} (3.5588E34J) = Z(1.45259E34J)$$

$$Z(1.45259E34J) = (2.92E34J)$$

$$Z = 2 \text{ protons} = \text{Helium}(He)$$

The equation for Saturn is then

$$8 \quad E = \frac{Z_{He}}{\sqrt{6}} \frac{G^2 M_s^2 M_m^3}{2 \hbar_{\odot}^2}$$

It makes sense that Saturn would use Helium in the equation because Saturn is the next planet after Jupiter and Jupiter uses hydrogen, and helium is the next element after hydrogen. As well, just like Jupiter, Saturn is primarily composed of hydrogen and helium gas.

Our equation in this paper for the Earth orbit does not depend on the Moon's distance from the Earth, only its mass. The Moon slows the Earth rotation and this in turn expands the Moon's orbit, so it is getting larger, the Earth loses energy to the Moon. The Earth day gets longer by 0.0067 hours per million years, and the Moon's orbit gets 3.78 cm larger per year. It is believed the Moon came from a chunk knocked off the Earth from a collision with a Mars sized protoplanet. At the time that the Moon formed it was about 4 Earth radii distant 4.5 billion years ago. After 100 million years the Moon became tidally locked making its rotation period equal to its orbital period keeping one face always towards the Earth. After 500 million years the Moon was orbiting at about 20 Earth radii. It is believed that during the period of heavy bombardment in a chaotic early solar system about 4.1 to 3.8 billion years ago a large object did a close pass pulling the Moon further changing its orbit giving it its 5 degree offset from the Earth's equator. Our wave equation solution may only use the Moon's mass but the equation for

kinetic energy of the Moon to kinetic energy of the Earth times the Earth Day equal to about one second:

$$\frac{KE_{moon}}{KE_{earth}}(EarthDay) = 1.08seconds$$

Which we connect with the equation where the proton gives one second

$$\frac{1}{6\alpha^2 m_p} \sqrt{\frac{h4\pi r_p^2}{Gc}} = 1.004996354seconds$$

This holds for when the Moon was at a distance from the Earth such that it appears the same size as the Sun, which means:

$$\frac{r_{planet}}{r_{moon}} \approx \frac{R_{star}}{R_{moon}}$$

Which is when the two equations above for one second connect to our wave equation solution to the Earth

$$KE_e = \sqrt{n} \frac{R_{\odot}}{R_m} \cdot \frac{G^2 M_e^2 M_m^3}{2\hbar_{\odot}^2}$$

$$\text{Because } \frac{R_{star}}{R_{moon}} = \frac{R_{\odot}}{R_m}.$$

The Moon at its inclination to the Earth in its orbit makes life possible here because it holds the Earth at its tilt to its orbit around the Sun allowing for the seasons so the Earth doesn't get too extremely hot or too extremely cold. We see the Moon may be there for a reason.

Part 6: Modeling Habitable Star Systems

Modeling Habitable Star Systems

We want to solve a habitable planetary system in general and apply it to another star system. We must include the solution of its moon as well, because the Moon of the Earth makes life optimally possible. However, our Moon is counter-intuitive, it breaks all of the rules of the other moons in our solar system. One is it has a low mass for its size. It has been said that it could be hollow. Even suggested that it is a hollow-spacecraft put there to make life as we know it possible. In our quantum theory for the solar system, we may have discovered the science of the engineers who may have made the Moon, and we are possibly applying their science here. Our quantum theory for the solar system also has a solar solution as compared to a lunar solution, so it works for star systems in general.

The perfect star system to use for our purposes here would be Tau Ceti. Tau Ceti is a star spectrally similar to the Sun and the closest of such a G-class star, at about 12 light years distant. Its mass is 78% of the Sun's. Its mass is

$$M_s = 0.783 + / - 0.012M_{\odot}$$

Its radius is:

$$R_s = 0.793 + / - 0.004R_{\odot}$$

And its luminosity is

$$L_s = 0.488 + / - 0.0010L_{\odot}$$

It has several unconfirmed planets with one potentially in the habitable zone. It has been the subject of science fiction literature. It is in the constellation Cetus. From Tau Ceti the Earth would be seen to be in the northern hemisphere constellation Bootes with an apparent magnitude of 2.6. It is spectral class G8 V where our Sun is G2 V.

For the luminosity of a main sequence star we only need to know the mass of the star to get its luminosity:

$$1 \quad L = M^{3.5}$$

This holds in solar masses and solar luminosities. The habitable zone of a star is given by luminosity. If the star is 100 times brighter than our Sun, then the habitable zone is 10 times further than the Earth is from the Sun by the inverse square law.

$$2 \quad r_p = \sqrt{L_s}$$

In astronomical units and solar luminosities. From r_p we can get the orbital period in Earth years:

$$3 \quad T_p^2 = r_p^3$$

We can get the radius of the Moon of the planet if we know the mass of the planet, M_e :

$$4 \quad \sqrt{2} \frac{R_{\odot}}{R_m} \sqrt{\frac{M_e}{M_{\odot}}} = 1$$

We want the mass of the Earth from the mass of the Sun. We would guess we can get it from the mass of the Sun, the size of the Sun, and the base 60 sexagesimal system upon which we have found everything is based. I find the relationship exists for the Earth:

$$5 \quad M_e = \frac{5}{6^2} M_{\odot} \frac{R_{\odot}^2}{r_e^2}$$

(36)(5)=180=360/2 and 360/6=60 is base 60 sexagesimal. This gives

$$M_e = 0.13889(1.9891E30kg) \frac{6.96E8m^2}{1.496E11m^2} = 5.979748E24kg$$

This is an accuracy of

$$\frac{5.972E24}{5.979748E24} 100 = 99.87 \%$$

We can get the orbital distance of the planet's Moon from the planet:

$$6 \quad \frac{r_{planet}}{r_{moon}} \approx \frac{R_{star}}{R_{moon}}$$

Once we have that we can get the radius of the Moon of the planet

$$7 \quad \sqrt{2} \frac{R_{\odot}}{R_m} \sqrt{\frac{M_e}{M_{\odot}}} = 1$$

Now we can get the rotation period of the planet, its length of day:

$$8 \quad EarthDay = \frac{2r_e}{v_m} \sqrt{\frac{M_m}{M_{\odot}}} \sqrt{3}$$

Because the orbital velocity of the planet's Moon is

$$9 \quad v_m = \sqrt{\frac{GM_e}{r_m}}$$

We can use the the delocalization time get the moon's mass, which is 1/2 the planet's year, with

$$10 \quad \tau = \frac{m_{moon}(2r_{moon})^2}{\hbar_s} \quad , \quad \text{See Appendix 1}$$

And the whole system is solved. Let us see how the theoretical luminosity appears with that measured with equation 8.1:

$$L_s = M_s^{3.5} = 0.783^{3.5} = 0.425L_{\odot}$$

It is close to the $0.448L_{\odot}$ measured. The equation for predicting is approximate as the actual values can vary a little with things like metallicity of the stars. Tau Ceti has low metallicity compared to our Sun.

Let's find the orbital distance of the habitable planet if it exists with equation 2:

$$r_p = \sqrt{0.488} = 0.69857AU = (0.6986AU)(1.496E11m/AU) = 1.045E11meters$$

Let's find the orbital period of the habitable planet (It's year) with equation 3:

$$T_p^2 = r_p^3, \quad T_p^2 = (0.69867AU)^3$$

$$T_p = 0.584years(365.25days)((24hrs)(60min)(60sec) = 1849638seconds$$

$$=(0.584)(365.25days) = 213.306days$$

Let's get the mass of the habitable planet from equation 5:

$$M_p = \frac{5}{36} M_s \frac{R_s^2}{r_p^2}$$

$$M_s = (0.783)(1.9891E30kg) = 1.5575E30kg$$

$$R_s = (0.793)(6.96E8m) = 5.52E8m$$

$$M_p = \frac{5}{36}(1.5575E30kg) \frac{(5.52E8m)^2}{(1.045E11m)^2} = 6.036E24kg$$

$$= \frac{6.036E24}{5.972E24} = 1.0107EarthMasses$$

Which is good because the planet, if it exists, is thought to be larger than the Earth. Let's get the radius of its moon from equation 4:

$$R_m = \sqrt{2}R_s \sqrt{\frac{M_p}{M_s}}$$

$$= \sqrt{2}(5.52E8m) \sqrt{\frac{(6.036E24kg)}{(1.5575E30kg)}} = 1.53656E6m = \frac{1.53656E6m}{1.7374E6m} = 0.8844LunarRadii$$

Let's see at what distance it orbits the planet with equation 6:

$$r_{moon} = r_{planet} \frac{R_{moon}}{R_{star}} = (1.045E11m) \frac{1.53656E6m}{5.52E8m} = 2.91E8m$$

$$= \frac{2.91E8m}{3.84E8m} = 0.7578 \text{ Lunar Orbital Radii}$$

Let's get the orbital velocity of this moon with equation 9:

$$v_m = \sqrt{\frac{GM_p}{r_m}} = \sqrt{\frac{(6.67408E-11)(6.0636E24kg)}{2.91E8m}} = 1,176.6m/s$$

So the orbital period of the moon is:

$$T_m = \frac{2\pi r_m}{v_m} = \frac{2\pi(.91E8m)}{1,176.6m/s} = 1.554E6seconds$$

$$= (1.554E6s) \frac{min}{60sec} \frac{hour}{60min} \frac{day}{24hours} = 17.987days$$

Compared to that of the Earth which is 27.3 days for the sidereal month and is a 29.53day lunar month. The Moon of Tau Ceti would have a slightly longer lunar month, too. Now we can determine the rotation period of the planet which would be its day:

We get the mass of the moon from equation 10:

$$M_m = \frac{\hbar_s \tau}{4r_m^2} = \frac{(2.8314E33J \cdot s)(0.5)(18429638s)}{4(2.91E8m)^2} = 7.7E22kg$$

$$= \frac{7.7E22kg}{7.34763E22kg} = 1.048 \text{ Earth Moons}$$

So the rotation period of the planet (Its Day) is from equation 8:

$$PlanetDay = \frac{2r_p}{v_m} \sqrt{\frac{M_m}{M_s}} \sqrt{3}$$

$$= \frac{2(1.045E11m)}{1,176.6m/s} \sqrt{\frac{7.7E22kg}{1.5575E30kg}} = 39495.61seconds = 658.26min = 10.971hours$$

$$= \frac{10.971}{24hours} = 0.457 \text{ Earth Days}$$

If the moon of Tau Ceti is to perfectly eclipse its star, like our Moon does with the Sun, to let its inhabitants know that they are there for reason, and so as to theoretically be a condition for optimizing life, then we have the following should hold:

$$\frac{r_{planet}}{r_{moon}} \approx \frac{R_{star}}{R_{moon}}$$

We have

$$\frac{1.045E11m}{2.91E8m} = \frac{5.52E8m}{1.53656E6m}$$

$$359 = 359$$

And it does hold. For the Earth/Moon/Sun system we get

$$400 = 400$$

For the Tau Ceti system the 359 is close to 360, which is a convenient amount of degrees into which divide a circle, like we did. We see the Tau Cetians might do the same, because like us they might choose the base 60 sexagesimal system of counting, and this 360 might influence the way the inhabitants of a planet orbiting this star would make their calendar. Just like the 365 day year here on Earth corresponds closely to the 360 degrees of a circle. Aside from having here on Earth the degree, we have gradians, of which there are 400 in a circle. They make it very easy for computing right angles to a given angle. They are used more in Europe and in surveying and architecture, though it might have some interesting connection with our 400=400.

The habitable planet of Tau Ceti would orbit its star with a period of 213 days, which would be its year. Its star is about 78% the mass of our Sun, and about 79% its size. Its habitable planet would be a little larger than the Earth, but not much. Its Moon would be about 88% the size of our moon, but a little bit more massive, but not much more massive. It would orbit Tau Ceti once about every 18 days meaning there would be 11.833 months in the Tau Ceti Year, or about 12 months like we have. It would orbit the planet at about three quarters the distance ours does. The day from sunrise to sunrise, or sunset to sunset would be about 11 hours, or close to half the length of our day. This is if Tau Ceti was engineered for life, but it doesn't have to have a planet so optimally designed for life as ours. Our 24 hour day would be better for when entering the realm of doing astronomy, because longer nights mean more complete observations of the universe surrounding us than for the Tau Cetians. It may mean for the conditions for life to be optimal, like here on Earth, the star would have to be as massive as the Sun, to provide a longer year and a longer day. But we see here how the science of engineering planetary systems optimal for life, might be done.

Appendix 1

If we want to prove that our planetary Planck constant is correct, the delocalization time for the Earth should be 6 months using it, the time for the Earth to travel the width of its orbit. We want to solve the Schrödinger wave equation for a wave packet and use the most basic thing we can which is a Gaussian distribution. We want to then substitute for Planck's constant h that is used for quanta and atoms our Planck-type constant \hbar_{\odot} (\hbar bar solar) for the Earth/Moon/Sun system then apply it to predict the delocalization time for the Moon in its orbit with the Earth around the Sun.

We consider a Gaussian wave-packet at $t=0$:

$$\psi(x,0) = A e^{-\frac{x^2}{2d^2}}$$

We say that d is the delocalization length and decompose the wave packet with a Fourier transform:

$$\psi(x,0) = A e^{-\frac{x^2}{2d^2}} = \int \frac{dp}{2\pi\hbar} \phi_p e^{\frac{i}{\hbar} px}$$

ϕ_p is the harmonics of the wave function. We use the identity that gives the integral of a quadratic:

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{-\alpha^2 x + \beta x} dx = \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{\alpha}} e^{\frac{\beta^2}{4\alpha}}$$

Solve the equation

$$i\hbar\partial_t\psi(x,t) = \frac{\hat{p}}{2m}\psi(x,t)$$

With the initial condition

$$\psi(x,0) = \int dp \cdot e^{\frac{p^2 d^2}{2\hbar^2}} \cdot e^{-\frac{i}{\hbar} px}$$

A plane wave is the solution:

$$e^{\frac{i}{\hbar}(px - \epsilon(p)t)}$$

$$\text{Where, } \epsilon(p) = \frac{p^2}{2m}$$

The wave-packet evolves with time as

$$\psi(x,t) = \int dp \cdot e^{\frac{p^2 d^2}{2\hbar^2}} \cdot e^{-\frac{i}{\hbar}(px - \frac{p^2}{2m}t)}$$

Calculate the Gaussian integral of dp

$$\alpha^2 = \frac{d^2}{2\hbar^2} + \frac{it}{2m\hbar} \text{ and } \beta = \frac{ix}{\hbar}$$

The solution is:

$$|\psi|^2 = \exp \left[-\frac{x^2}{d^2} \cdot \frac{1}{1 + t^2/\tau^2} \right] \text{ where } \tau = \frac{md^2}{\hbar}$$

d is the delocalization distance, which for instance could be the width of an atom. τ is the delocalization time, the average time for say an electron to traverse the diameter of the atom and even leave it, to delocalize. If we substitute for \hbar our \hbar_{\odot} , and say that the delocalization distance is for the Moon, the width of the Earth orbit, we should get a half a year for the delocalization time, the time for the Moon and Earth to traverse the diameter of their orbit around the Sun. We have

$$\tau = \frac{m_{moon}(2r_{moon})^2}{\hbar_{\odot}}$$

Where m_{moon} is the mass of the Moon, and r_{moon} is the orbital radius of the Moon. We have

$$\tau = 4 \frac{(7.34767E22kg)(3.844E8m)^2}{2.8314E33J \cdot s} = 15338227 \text{ seconds}$$

Now let's compute a half a year...

$$(1/2)(365.25)(24)(60)(60) = 15778800 \text{ seconds}$$

So we see our delocalization time is very close to the half year over which the Earth and Moon travel from one position to the opposite side of the Sun. The closeness is

$$\frac{15338227}{15778800} 100 = 97.2 \%$$

Thus we know our \hbar_{\odot} is accurate, it continues to function in a theoretical framework. The thing about this is that it means we can predict the mass of the Moon from the Earth year. In terms of what we said earlier that the Moon allows for life by creating the seasons, holding the Earth at its tilt to the Sun, so we don't go through extreme heat and cold, this suggests the Moon has a mass that follows from Earth orbit, which is the habitable zone of the Sun, the right distance for water to exist as liquid, and thus could be as it is for a reason, which means life might be part of a physical process throughout the Universe, that it unfolds naturally in the evolution of star systems.

Appendix 2: The Data For Verifying The Equations

$m_p: 1.67262 \times 10^{-27} \text{ kg}$ (Proton Mass)

$h: 6.62607 \times 10^{-34} \text{ J} \cdot \text{s}$ (Planck Constant)

$r_p: 0.833 \times 10^{-15} \text{ m}$ (Proton Radius)

$G: 6.67408 \times 10^{-11} \text{ N} \frac{\text{m}^2}{\text{kg}^2}$ (Gravitational Constant)

$c : 299,792,458 \text{ m/s}$ (light speed)

$\alpha: 1/137$ (Fine Structure Constant)

$q_p = q_e = 1.6022 \text{ E} - 19 \text{ coulombs}$

$k_e = 8.988 \text{ E} 9 \frac{\text{Nm}^2}{\text{C}^2}$

Earth day=(24)(60)(60)=86,400 seconds. Using the Moon's orbital velocity at aphelion, and Earth's orbital velocity at perihelion we have:

$$KE_{moon} = \frac{1}{2}(7.347673 \text{ E} 22 \text{ kg})(966 \text{ m/s})^2 = 3.428 \text{ E} 28 \text{ J}$$

$$KE_{earth} = \frac{1}{2}(5.972 \text{ E} 24 \text{ kg})(30,290 \text{ m/s})^2 = 2.7396 \text{ E} 33 \text{ J}$$

The Author

